

**Synthesis of Steroidal Oxazolidones of
Androstane Series**

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IN view of the useful pharmacological and biological activities¹ of oxazolidones and in continuation of our earlier work on steroidal oxazolidones², the present work was undertaken.

3-Substituted-17-oxo androstane, i.e. 17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -yl acetate (1a), 3 β -chloro-17-oxo-5-androstene³ (1b), 17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -ol (1c), 17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -methyl ether³ (1d) and 17-oxo-5-androsten-3 β -ethyl ether (1e) were reacted with semicarbazide hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate to form the corresponding 17-semicarbazones (2a-e), whose ir spectra gave significant peaks at 3 300-3 200 (NH₂, NH), 1 640 (C=N) and 1 670 cm⁻¹ (CONH).

Compounds 2a-e on treatment with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished the oxazolidone which could have either structure 3 or 4. The characterisation of the product as 5-androsten-20-hydrazino-(1',3'-oxazolin-2'-yliden-4'-one)-3 β -yl acetate³ (3a), 3 β -chloro-5-androsten-20-hydrazino(1',3'-oxazolin-2'-yliden-4'-one) (3b), 5-androsten-20-hydrazino(1',3'-oxazolin-2'-yliden-4'-one)-3 β -ol (3c), 5-androsten-20-hydrazino(1',3'-oxazolin-2'-yliden-4'-one)-3 β -methyl ether (3d) and 5-androsten-20-hydrazino(1',3'-oxazolin-2'-yliden-4'-one)-3 β -ethyl ether (3e) rather than 4a-e respectively, was based on spectral data: $\nu_{\max}$ 3 250 (NH), 1 680 (CONH), 1 715 (C=O of oxazolidone ring) and 1 645 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 7.2 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable, NH), 5.3 (1H, m, C₈-vinylic), 4.1 (2H, s, CH₂ of oxazolidone), 3.8 (1H, br m, W_{1/2} 10 Hz, C₃-OH)⁴. The conclusive evidence in support of structure 3a-e was afforded by ¹³C nmr spectral data: δ 185 (CONH), 156.8 (C=N), 140.0 (C₆-olefin) and 73.2 (CH₂ of oxazolidone ring). The alternative structures 4a-e would have given the ¹³C nmr peak of CH₂ oxazolidone at δ 65.0.

Experimental

All the m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1371 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra(CDCl₃) on a Varian A 60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL FX-100 (25.00 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Petroleum ether refers to a fraction of b.p. 60-80°. Physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	δ
3a	230-32	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄ N ₂	7.25 (1H, s, NH, D ₂ O exchangeable), 5.3 (1H, m, C ₈ -vinylic), 3.8 (1H, br m, W _{1/2} 10 Hz, C ₃ -OH) ⁴ , 4.1 (2H, s, CH ₂ of oxazolidone)
3b	114-16	C ₂₃ H ₃₆ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	7.3 (1H, s, NH, D ₂ O exchangeable), 5.2 (1H, m, vinylic), 4.0 (2H, s, CH ₂ of oxazolidone), 3.7 (1H, br m, W _{1/2} 10 Hz, C ₃ -OH)
3c	123-25	C ₂₃ H ₃₈ O ₄ N ₂	7.2 (1H, s, NH, D ₂ O), 5.3 (1H, m, vinylic), 4.1 (2H, s, CH ₂ of oxazolidone), 3.8 (1H, m, C ₃ -OH)
3d	136-38	C ₂₅ H ₃₈ O ₄ N ₂	7.2 (1H, s, NH, D ₂ O exchangeable), 5.2 (1H, m, vinylic), 4.0 (2H, s, CH ₂ of oxazolidone), 3.4 (3H, s, OCH ₃)
3e	143-45	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ O ₄ N ₂	7.15 (1H, s, NH, D ₂ O), 5.25 (1H, m, vinylic), 4.0 (2H, s, CH ₂ of oxazolidone), 5.1 (3H, t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.2 (2H, q, OCH ₂ CH ₃)

*All compounds gave satisfactory results for C, H and N analyses.

17-Semicarbazones (2a-e): To the ketones (1a-e; 1.0 g) in ethanol (30 ml) were added semicarbazide hydrochloride (3 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (5 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. After usual work-up, the products were crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystalline solids.

5-Androsten-20-hydrazino(1',3'-oxazolin-2'-yliden-4'-one)-3 β -yl acetate (3a-e): To the 17-semicarbazones (2a-e; 1.0 g) in acetic acid (35 ml) were added chloroacetic acid (0.25 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.35 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 7 h. Usual work-up afforded a solid, which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g). Elution with petroleum ether gave the unreacted compound and further elution with benzene afforded the products (Table 1).

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NOTES

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